

Survey questionnaire

Survey questionnaire section 1 of 4.

- (1) Which formalism, notation or means is useful for documentation and presentation purposes in **analytics modeling**, and for the communication of **data scientists** with their peers? Please select all that may apply. You may use the optional text fields for any further remarks.

Hint: Data scientists are responsible for analytics modeling. They either create new algorithms, techniques and methods or adapt and use existing ones to create data analytics and machine learning models, for example, for prediction or clustering.

- Computational Graphs (CG), also known as Data-Flow Graphs (DFG)
- UML Class diagram
- Mathematical notation, showing the mathematical model (e.g., probability distributions, the objective/loss function, etc.)
- Dataflow diagram (e.g., using the UML Activity diagram notation) showing the upstream and downstream components in the pipeline
- Charts/diagrams/plots (e.g., histograms, pie charts, scatter plots, etc.)
- Probabilistic Graphical Models (PGM)
- Entity-Relationship (ER) diagram
- Topic Maps and/or Knowledge Graphs (e.g., RDF Graphs) and/or Ontologies
- Others (please specify)

- (2) Which formalism, notation or means is useful for documentation and presentation purposes in **analytics operations**, and for the communication of **data engineers** with their peers? Please select all that may apply. You may use the optional text fields for any further remarks.

Hint: Data engineers are responsible for analytics operations. They create, adapt and maintain scoring engines (i.e., model consumers), and are concentrated on large-scale batch/stream data processing, for example, using the Apache Hadoop/Spark ecosystems or similar big data analytics platforms and technologies. Data engineers should not be confused with database engineers/designers.

- Computational Graphs (CG), also known as Data-Flow Graphs (DFG)
- UML Class diagram
- Mathematical notation, showing the mathematical model (e.g., probability distributions, the objective/loss function, etc.)
- Dataflow diagram (e.g., using the UML Activity diagram notation) showing the workflows/pipelines
- Charts/diagrams/plots (e.g., histograms, pie charts, scatter plots, etc.)
- Probabilistic Graphical Models (PGM)
- Entity-Relationship (ER) diagram
- Topic Maps and/or Knowledge Graphs (e.g., RDF Graphs) and/or Ontologies
- Others (please specify)

- (3) When you look at a smart software/information system or enterprise as a **data scientist**, which information about the software/system/enterprise would you like to see to be able to describe the architecture?

Hint: Each stakeholder or group of stakeholders often have their own understanding and viewpoint/view, thus focus on different aspects.

- The computational operations and the flow of data among them
- The processes and/or components, and the flow of data among them
- The processes and/or components, and the flow of control among them
- The underlying mathematical model
- The data visualization (e.g., in the case of online learning / stream processing)
- The workflow/pipeline for data analytics and machine learning
- The problem/use-case domain concepts and their relationships
- Others (please specify)

- (4) When you look at a smart software/information system or enterprise as a **data engineer**, which information about the software/system/enterprise would you like to see to be able to describe the architecture?

Hint: Each stakeholder or group of stakeholders often have their own understanding and viewpoint/view, thus focus on different aspects.

- The computational operations and the flow of data among them
- The processes and/or components, and the flow of data among them
- The processes and/or components, and the flow of control among them
- The underlying mathematical model
- The data visualization (e.g., in the case of online learning / stream processing)
- The workflow/pipeline for data analytics and machine learning
- The problem/use-case domain concepts and their relationships
- Others (please specify)

Survey questionnaire section 2 of 4.

- 1 (1) Which formalism, notation or means is useful for the communication of data scientists and data engineers with the **end-users** of
2 software and information systems? Please select all that may apply. You may use the optional text fields for any further remarks.

3 *Hint: End-users are one of the key stakeholders of software and information systems.*

- 4 • Tables/matrices
- 5 • Probabilistic Graphical Models (PGM)
- 6 • Topic Maps and/or Knowledge Graphs (e.g., RDF Graphs) and/or Ontologies
- 7 • UML Use Case diagram
- 8 • Entity-Relationship (ER) diagram
- 9 • Charts/diagrams/plots (e.g., histograms, pie charts, scatter plots, etc.)
- 10 • Dataflow diagram (e.g., using the UML Activity diagram notation)
- 11 • Text document
- 12 • Mathematical notation, showing the mathematical model (e.g., probability distributions, the objective/loss function, etc.)
- 13 • UML Class diagram
- 14 • Computational Graphs (CG), also known as Data-Flow Graphs (DFG)
- 15 • Others (please specify)

- 16 (2) Which formalism, notation or means is useful for the communication of data scientists and data engineers with the **business**
17 **stakeholders** of software and information systems? Please select all that may apply. You may use the optional text fields for any
18 further remarks.

19 *Hint: Business stakeholders are one of the key stakeholders of software, information systems and enterprises. Examples include, but are*
20 *not limited to the upper-level/middle management, the CTO/CEO, etc.*

- 21 • Tables/matrices
- 22 • Probabilistic Graphical Models (PGM)
- 23 • Topic Maps and/or Knowledge Graphs (e.g., RDF Graphs) and/or Ontologies
- 24 • UML Use Case diagram
- 25 • Entity-Relationship (ER) diagram
- 26 • Charts/diagrams/plots (e.g., histograms, pie charts, scatter plots, etc.)
- 27 • Dataflow diagram (e.g., using the UML Activity diagram notation)
- 28 • Text document
- 29 • Mathematical notation, showing the mathematical model (e.g., probability distributions, the objective/loss function, etc.)
- 30 • UML Class diagram
- 31 • Computational Graphs (CG), also known as Data-Flow Graphs (DFG)
- 32 • Others (please specify)

- 33 (3) Which formalism, notation or means is useful for the communication of data scientists and data engineers with **safety and regulatory**
34 **compliance engineers, data protection (privacy) officers and ethics committees/boards**? Please select all that may apply. You
35 may use the optional text fields for any further remarks.

36 *Hint: This is about responsibility. Safety and regulatory compliance, data protection (privacy), and ethical aspects, including inclusiveness,*
37 *fairness and explainability of AI/DEA/ML are becoming increasingly important.*

- 38 • Tables/matrices
- 39 • Probabilistic Graphical Models (PGM)
- 40 • Topic Maps and/or Knowledge Graphs (e.g., RDF Graphs) and/or Ontologies
- 41 • UML Use Case diagram
- 42 • Entity-Relationship (ER) diagram
- 43 • Charts/diagrams/plots (e.g., histograms, pie charts, scatter plots, etc.)
- 44 • Dataflow diagram (e.g., using the UML Activity diagram notation)
- 45 • Text document
- 46 • Mathematical notation, showing the mathematical model (e.g., probability distributions, the objective/loss function, etc.)
- 47 • UML Class diagram
- 48 • Computational Graphs (CG), also known as Data-Flow Graphs (DFG), for example, augmented with the deployment details (i.e.,
49 on which GPU/CPU core)
- 50 • Others (please specify)

- 51 (4) Which formalism, notation or means is useful for the communication of data scientists and data engineers with **database engi-**
52 **neers/designers**? Please select all that may apply. You may use the optional text fields for any further remarks.

53 *Hint: Database engineers/designers should not be confused with data engineers. Database engineers/designers are concerned with Database*
54 *Management Systems (DBMS).*

- 55 • Tables/matrices
- 56 • Probabilistic Graphical Models (PGM)
- 57 • Topic Maps and/or Knowledge Graphs (e.g., RDF Graphs) and/or Ontologies

117	• UML Use Case diagram	175
118	• Entity-Relationship (ER) diagram	176
119	• Charts/diagrams/plots (e.g., histograms, pie charts, scatter plots, etc.)	177
120	• Dataflow diagram (e.g., using the UML Activity diagram notation)	178
121	• Text document	179
122	• Mathematical notation, showing the mathematical model (e.g., probability distributions, the objective/loss function, etc.)	180
123	• UML Class diagram	181
124	• Computational Graphs (CG), also known as Data-Flow Graphs (DFG)	182
125	• Others (please specify)	183
126	(5) Which formalism, notation or means is useful for the communication of data scientists and data engineers with software engineers	184
127	and software architects ? Please select all that may apply. You may use the optional text fields for any further remarks.	185
128	<i>Hint: Software engineers have the development viewpoint and are primarily concerned with the actual software module organization,</i>	186
129	<i>layers, libraries and APIs, etc. A proper communication between the DEA/ML experts and software engineers is crucial.</i>	187
130	• Tables/matrices	188
131	• Probabilistic Graphical Models (PGM)	189
132	• Topic Maps and/or Knowledge Graphs (e.g., RDF Graphs) and/or Ontologies	190
133	• UML Use Case diagram	191
134	• Entity-Relationship (ER) diagram	192
135	• Charts/diagrams/plots (e.g., histograms, pie charts, scatter plots, etc.)	193
136	• Dataflow diagram (e.g., using the UML Activity diagram notation)	194
137	• Text document	195
138	• Mathematical notation, showing the mathematical model (e.g., probability distributions, the objective/loss function, etc.)	196
139	• UML Class diagram	197
140	• Computational Graphs (CG), also known as Data-Flow Graphs (DFG)	198
141	• Others (please specify)	199
142	(6) Which formalism, notation or means is useful for the communication of data scientists and data engineers with system engineers	200
143	and network experts ? Please select all that may apply. You may use the optional text fields for any further remarks.	201
144	<i>Hint: System engineers are concerned with the system configuration from a physical viewpoint; being primarily interested in the</i>	202
145	<i>deployment of software components on the hardware resources, as well as the non-functional requirements, such as availability, reliability</i>	203
146	<i>(i.e., fault-tolerance), throughput, and scalability. Similarly, network experts are concerned with various layers of computer networks.</i>	204
147	• Tables/matrices	205
148	• Probabilistic Graphical Models (PGM)	206
149	• Topic Maps and/or Knowledge Graphs (e.g., RDF Graphs) and/or Ontologies	207
150	• UML Use Case diagram	208
151	• Entity-Relationship (ER) diagram	209
152	• Charts/diagrams/plots (e.g., histograms, pie charts, scatter plots, etc.)	210
153	• Dataflow diagram (e.g., using the UML Activity diagram notation)	211
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155	• Mathematical notation, showing the mathematical model (e.g., probability distributions, the objective/loss function, etc.)	213
156	• UML Class diagram	214
157	• Computational Graphs (CG), also known as Data-Flow Graphs (DFG), for example, augmented with the deployment details (i.e.,	215
158	on which GPU/CPU core)	216
159	• Others (please specify)	217
160	(7) Which formalism, notation or means is useful for the communication of data scientists and data engineers with security experts ?	218
161	Please select all that may apply. You may use the optional text fields for any further remarks.	219
162	<i>Hint: In DEA/ML, security comprises new aspects regarding the data analytics and machine learning models, for example, the adversarial</i>	220
163	<i>attack resistance/robustness of the ML models.</i>	221
164	• Tables/matrices	222
165	• Probabilistic Graphical Models (PGM)	223
166	• Topic Maps and/or Knowledge Graphs (e.g., RDF Graphs) and/or Ontologies	224
167	• UML Use Case diagram	225
168	• Entity-Relationship (ER) diagram	226
169	• Charts/diagrams/plots (e.g., histograms, pie charts, scatter plots, etc.)	227
170	• Dataflow diagram (e.g., using the UML Activity diagram notation)	228
171	• Text document	229
172	• Mathematical notation, showing the mathematical model (e.g., probability distributions, the objective/loss function, etc.)	230
173	• UML Class diagram	231
174		232

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- Others (please specify)

Survey questionnaire section 3 of 4.

- (1) On a scale of 1 to 5, how much is each stakeholder affected by Artificial Intelligence (AI), specifically Machine Learning (ML) as well as Data Engineering and Analytics (DEA)? 1 means not at all (i.e., no impact), and 5 means the highest level of impact.

Hint: Please select your best own estimation. If you are not sure, you may select no answer.

- (a) ethics committees/boards
- (b) data protection (privacy) officers
- (c) data engineers
- (d) database engineers/designers
- (e) business stakeholders
- (f) safety and regulatory compliance engineers
- (g) data scientists (including Machine Learning engineers)
- (h) software engineers and software architects
- (i) domain/knowledge engineers
- (j) end-users
- (k) security experts

- (2) Are you aware of any stakeholder(s) with concerns with respect to Artificial Intelligence (AI), specifically Machine Learning (ML) as well as Data Engineering and Analytics (DEA), whom we have not mentioned so far?

Hint: Please use the text fields below and mention each of them in one text area. Please state their roles and briefly explain how they are affected by AI/ML/DEA.

Survey questionnaire section 4 of 4.

- (1) What is your sex/gender?

- (a) Female
- (b) Male
- (c) Other

- (2) What is your age group?

- (a) Below 18
- (b) 18-24
- (c) 25-39
- (d) 40-60
- (e) 60 plus

- (3) What is your highest academic degree?

Hint: Please select the one that is already conferred by a recognized higher education institute (university).

- (a) Bachelor's
- (b) Master's
- (c) PhD
- (d) No academic degree
- (e) (optional) Make a comment on your choice here.

- (4) What is your educational background? Please select all that may apply.

Hint: If you have multiple backgrounds, please indicate the one that is most relevant to your current job. Also, if you have multiple jobs, please consider your main job (i.e., the one in which you spend the majority of your working time in a week or month).

- (a) No higher (i.e., university-level) education
- (b) Computer Science/Computer Engineering: AI/Machine Learning/Data Science/Data Analytics/Data Engineering
- (c) Computer Science/Computer Engineering: Software Engineering
- (d) Computer Science/Computer Engineering: other sub-disciplines
- (e) Other engineering fields (please specify)
- (f) Physics
- (g) Mathematics / Statistics
- (h) Other fields or disciplines

- (5) What is your current job or occupation?

Hint: If you have multiple jobs, please indicate the main one (i.e., in which you spend the majority of your working time in a week or month).

- Manager

